

ICCFMS – Set Up Candid Clips Effectiveness

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Abstract—The objectives were to analyze the using of new media in the form of set up candid clip that affects the product and presenter, to study the effectiveness of using new media in the form of set up candid clip in order to increase the circulation and audience satisfaction and to use the earned information and knowledge to develop the communication for publicizing and advertising via new media. This research is qualitative research based on questionnaire and in-depth interview from experts. The findings showed the advantages and disadvantages of communication for publicizing and advertising via new media in the form of set up candid clip including with the specific target group for this kind of advertising. It will be useful for fields of publicizing and advertising in the new media forms at the present.

Keywords—Candid Clip, Communication, New Media, Social Network.

I. INTRODUCTION

AS we know that publicizing and advertising are very important in the competitive world at the present. The main purposes of publicizing and advertising are to; increase sales and profits, encourage trial and usage and remind advertising. We all are surrounded by many media such as press, television, radio, cinema for more than 100 years. At the present, there're new media that is used via internet or social network and mobile devices such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube, LINE and etc. Social media is a form of communication that accessible to all levels of people in short time which spread out extensively around the world at the present under the whole time development of computer technology. Social media tends to be priority media for people in the future. [4]

Fig. 1 Berlo's SMCR model of communication [1]

Basic elements of persuasion consist of the external view of receiver (internal difference of sender, internal difference of message, difference of media and internal difference of

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situation) and receiver (demography, attitude, knowledge, emotions, importance of issue and means of perception) [3]. All factors affect the effectiveness of communication via media.

Matrix of communication for persuasion is divided into independent variable which is communication and dependent variable which is attitude or behavior changing. [5] Communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is independent variable in this study.

At the present, communication via new media is popular in every field such as celebrities, politicians, academicians, etc. Since the communication via new media is potential in the ways of speed of time and accessibility to the majority of the population.

Viral marketing is one of the important issues in this study. Viral marketing is popular for marketing communication via new media which this kind of marketing must reside social networks. [2] Because of the trend of advertising nowadays that cheap budget and quick communication in wide range are on demand. Then, viral marketing is the way that makes the brand or product can do the publicizing and advertising in lower budget and reach the majority audience rapidly.

We've noticed the trend of viral marketing that many of them combine with communication via new media. We've seen both positive and negative feedback from the audience of communication via new media especially in the form of set up candid clip.

According to the significance of communication, viral marketing, the technology development that cause the new potential media and the different feedback from the audience, the researches have to study the effectiveness of the new media communication in the form of set up candid clip in detail for further proper methods to use this kind of new media for the best function and effectiveness in the future.

II. PURPOSES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of this study were to analyze the using of new media in the form of set up candid clip that affects the product and presenter, to study the effectiveness of using new media in the form of set up candid clip in order to increase the circulation and audience satisfaction and to use the earned information and knowledge to develop the communication for publicizing and advertising via new media.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was a qualitative research arising from content analysis from the set up candid clips that were used as new media for publicizing and advertising via social network of 2 products in Thailand which are **Scotch 100** Essence of Chicken (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tZ_vaoO2eCo&

list=PLk68a1djsw1uLt-13FgotqMP5va9tFv9N&index=1) and **Snickers** Chocolate (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4v1haaj-ggU> and <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mz83sYATHbM&list=PLk68a1djsw1uLt-13FgotqMP5va9tFv9N&index=3>), questionnaire, in-depth interview, documents, literature and relevant research work. At first in methodology plan, the researchers would like to ask for product circulation from Scotch 100 and Snickers before, during and after the set up candid clip were launched. But both companies denied giving the product circulation because it's confidential. Another research tool is questionnaire which used both close and open ended by spreading out random sampling questionnaire which was made from Google Docs (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/16r87beTEYcEK_n7PfQECQEos3ZaCIWiyIplvZjttO_Qk/viewform) to get 50 representative samples' answers via social network which were Facebook and LINE. A strength, weakness, opportunity and threat (SWOT) methodology was employed as an analysis tool for in-depth interview from 2 experts in advertising and publicizing fields which the questions are open ended.

IV. RESULT OF THE STUDY

For 3 set up candid clips that were used as new media for publicizing and advertising via social network of 2 products in Thailand, Scotch 100 (1 clip) and Snickers (2 clips) analysis, the story of each clip are as following;

Scotch 100 Essence of Chicken (The presenter of this clip of Scotch 100 is a very famous actor in Thailand named Ananda Everingham. The situation was set in the advertising film production in studio around 4AM after the last scene of that advertising film shooting.)

Fig. 2 Assistant Director came to talk with Ananda and asked him to take 1 more shooting as special scene for this advertising film. He was asked to dance Gangnam Style (Korean famous music with the dancing style of the singer named Psy)

Fig. 3 Ananda was mad and screamed to everyone because the director said that the shooting was finished already. At that time, it's 4AM in the morning. They'd been worked too long time and he's not impressed about shooting another special scene for this advertising film that the assistant director asked him to do. He threw the water bottle and scolded to everyone that he's made fame for 10 years but how come the production team asked him to do stupid dance

Fig. 4 Instantly, Ananda danced Gangnam Style and all the production team danced with him seriously and joyfully

Fig. 5 Letters on screen "Give it 100% best shot in every life roles"

According to Youtube.com statistic, there're 728,509 views for this clip, which 8,552 people pressed "like" for this clip and 139 people pressed "unlike" for this clip (checked on 10 February, 2014).

Snickers Chocolate Clip No.1 (The presenter of this clip of Snickers is a moderate famous actress in Thailand named Aom Sucha Manaying. The situation was set in the mall that the presenter was working. She walked by to see her fans and her fans were screaming her name and would like to take pictures with her.)

Fig. 6 Aom Sucha met her fans while she was working at that mall

Fig. 7 Aom Sucha screamed to her fans after they screamed her name too loud and would like to take pictures with her

Fig. 8 One of the fans ran to her with her name electronic display. Aom Sucha pushed her and the electronic display fell. All fans raised their voice shockedly

According to Youtube.com statistic, there're 36,628 views for this clip, which 63 people pressed "like" for this clip and 54 people pressed "unlike" for this clip (checked on 10 February, 2014).

Snickers Chocolate Clip No.2 (The presenter of this clip is the same person as the 1st one named Aom Sucha Manaying.

The situation was set in the dressing room in the mall that she walked in after having problem with her fans.)

Fig. 9 Letters on screen "Don't let hungriness make you're not yourself"

Fig. 10 Aom Sucha complained about everything around her

Fig. 11 One staff ran into the dressing room and asked what happen to her

Fig. 12 Aom Sucha had Snickers in her hand and said sorry for getting mad because of hungriness. She's fine now

Fig. 13 Letter on screen “Don’t let hunger change you. When you need snack, you need Snickers”

According to Youtube.com statistic, there’re 319,609 views for this clip, which 893 people pressed “like” for this clip and 1,002 people pressed “unlike” for this clip. (checked on 10 February, 2014)

For the result of questionnaire, there’re 50 representative samples by random sampling. The questions are divided into 3 parts. There’re 3 close ended questions in the first part of personal information. There’re 10 close ended questions in the second part of experience, satisfaction and attitude before watching 3 set up candid clips. There’re 9 close ended questions and 1 open ended question in the third part of experience, satisfaction and attitude after watching 3 set up candid clips. The result of the questionnaire is as following;

Fig. 14 Genders and ages of 50 representative samples

Fig. 15 Level of education of 50 representative samples

Fig. 16 Result from 50 representative samples before watching 3 set up candid clips of Scotch 100 and Snickers

Fig. 17 Result from 50 representative samples after watching 3 set up candid clips of Scotch 100 and Snickers

There’re 22 people (44%) who like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip and 28 people (56%) who don’t like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip.

For the result of in-depth interview from 2 experts in advertising and publicizing fields, they have 6-8 year experience in advertising and publicizing and won many international advertising awards including Cannes 2012. They used to work on viral marketing project which used the new media for publicizing and advertising via social network but they haven’t worked in the form of set up candid clip. They think that people like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is because of the new and strange presentation form and the reason that people don’t like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is because people don’t like to get deceived. The strengths of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip are getting awareness overnight and get followed by the realistic set up. The weakness of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is bad brand image in case of bad content. The opportunity of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is in good direction if it’s based on good content, not too violent form. The threats of communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip are the bad content which cause bad image to the brand and audience emotions including consumers’

rejection which would not worth the investment for this kind of publicizing and advertising.

V. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

As the findings of this study from content analysis, result of questionnaire and in-depth interview, we can conclude that communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is rather effective way of communication in quick awareness getting (talk of the town) but in short period of time (short-term trend). It would be suitable for the product or brand that requires reminding to the product or brand by not concern about positive or negative feedback.

Communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is effective about satisfaction to female more than male, in the age of 31-35 and 41+ more than the other ages and in the level of education of secondary education more than the other levels of education.

Both Scotch 100 and Snickers' set up candid clips were effective in awareness and satisfaction to the audience. But the effectiveness of satisfaction of Snickers' set up candid clip is less than Scotch 100's.

Both Scotch 100 and Snickers' set up candid clips were not effective in circulation increase. On the contrary, they decrease the circulation of Scotch 100 and Snickers evaluated by result of questionnaire. But Snickers set up candid clip cause lower circulation than Scotch 100's.

According to the analysis of open ended question about the reasons that representative samples like or don't like communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip, it can be divided into 3 groups which are positive reasons, negative reasons and neutral reasons or no comment. Communication via new media in the form of set up candid clip is still rather effective in communicating with audience.

The conclusion from in-depth interview from 2 experts, we can conclude that the content is more important than the trend. Communication via new media should be based on good content in proper form. Because the set up candid clip in some issues are too sensitive to some target group audience. It can cause disappointment to the audience leading to bad image to the brand or product which will decrease the circulation and satisfaction from the customers. Communication via new media is a lot cheaper than other media but serious consideration of content and form is highly required.

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